

THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF RASAUSHADHIS IN SKIN DISEASES – A CRITICAL REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Skin diseases are among the most common health concerns worldwide. Globally, skin disease has shown to be fourth leading non-fatal disease worldwide. Often causing physical discomfort, psychological stress, and social stigma. Ayurveda, with its holistic approach, emphasizes both internal purification and external healing. Rasaushadhis are the Herbo mineral or metal or mineral formulations which occupy a unique place in Ayurvedic therapeutics due to their High potency, Low dose, rapid action, and ability to target chronic and complex conditions. Classical texts describe their role in Kushta through formulations such as Gandhaka Rasayana, Rasa Manikaya, Arogyavardhini Rasa, Vyadhiharana Rasa etc. Some Bhasma like Hartala Bhasma, Abhraka Bhasma, Loha Bhasma, Yashada Bhasma, Vanga Bhasma etc. plays important role in skin disease. These medicines act by correcting dosha imbalance,

purifying blood (Rakta Sodhana), enhancing immunity (OjasVardhana), and promoting tissue regeneration (Dhatu Poshana). Modern pharmacological studies highlight their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory properties, supporting their traditional use. When standardized and administered with proper safety protocols, Rasaushadhis offer promising integrative solutions for conditions like psoriasis, eczema, vitiligo, acne, and chronic dermatitis. This study will explore the role of Rasaushadhis in skin

diseases and determine which Rasaushadhi should be used in different Avasthas of the disease.

KEYWORDS – Rasaushadhi, Bhasma, Skin disease, Kustha.

INTRODUCTION

Rasaushadhis are the herbo-mineral, mineral or metal formulations which are used for therapeutic purpose. In Ayurvedic practice the Rasaushadhis has been considered as more effective and beneficial due to lesser therapeutic doses, enhancement of action of other ingredients of formulation, more shelf life, quicker action and palatability as compared to herbal preparation.^[1] Rasaushadhis are being the backbone of Ayurveda due to its Rasayana and therapeutic properties. The assimilation of Rasa preparations in the body is much faster because the preparation undergoes different processes called Samskaras. This helps in active and quick assimilation of even the minute doses in the body.

The skin is the largest organ of the human body, forming a protective covering on the outside and serving as the first line of defence against external factors. In Ayurveda, it is considered one of the principal sense organs. Globally, dermatological concerns are highly prevalent - around one - fifth of individuals who seek medical consultation each year present with skin-related issues, including cosmetic conditions. These disorders affect people across all age groups, from infants to the elderly, and often lead not only to physical discomfort but also to psychological distress and social stigma.^[2] Modern dermatology has advanced considerably in areas such as diagnostic techniques, immunotherapy, and the development of targeted medications. Yet, challenges remain-prolonged use of corticosteroids or immunosuppressive agents often produces adverse effects, while issues of recurrence and chronicity are still unresolved. These limitations have encouraged interest in integrative systems of medicine that address both internal imbalances and external symptoms. According to Ayurveda, disorders of the skin (Twak) are viewed as reflections of systemic disharmony involving the Doshas (Vata, Pitta, Kapha), the Dhatus, and the function of Agni. Classical texts group chronic and complex skin diseases under the category of Kushta, highlighting the need for purification, blood detoxification, rejuvenation, and lifestyle regulation. Unlike modern approaches that primarily target symptoms, Ayurveda emphasizes a root - cause methodology, combining preventive, promotive, curative, and rehabilitative strategies for holistic management. Rasaushadhis hold a significant place in the Ayurvedic management of skin disorders.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

1. To briefly explore the concept of Skin disease W.S.R. to Kushta.
2. To compile important Rasaushadhis mentioned in different classics for Kushta.
3. To explore important Rasa Dravyas and their importance, which are commonly used in Skin diseases (Kushta).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

For this study, Ayurveda classical text like Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Rasa Tarangini, Rasa Tantra Sara va Siddha Prayoga Sangraha etc. has been used to evaluate the concepts. Various related websites, journals have been searched.

Kushta

According to Amarakosha, the etymology of the word Kushta is derived from the root 'Kush' which means that comes from the inner part. The meaning can be understood by the appearance of affected Twacha because of the vitiation in the factors like Rakta, Mams, Lasika, Ambu and Tridoshas of the body(Saptako dravya sangraha).

Acharya Vagbhata has defined the Kushta Roga as that which causes Vaivarnya and Dushti to the Twacha.^[3]

The Ayurvedic medical system describes a wide spectrum of etiological factors of dermatological diseases. Etiological factors include physical, physiological, hereditary, psychological, psychosocial and papa-karma (sinful activities/psychosocial stress and related psychological factors are mainly responsible for the manifestation and/or aggravation of many dermatological diseases), etc.

Samprapti of Kushta

Kushta is a Tridoshajanya vyadhi. It is believed that this roga can't manifest with a single dosha involvement. The classification of Kushta is based on the Anshashakalpana of dosha. The Sapta dravyas of Kushta are Tridoshas, Twak, Rakta, Mamsa and Ambu. According to Acharya Charaka, Nidana Sevana leads to Prakopa of Tridosha and thus the vitiated Doshas will get Ashraya in Twak, Rakta, Mamsa and Ambu causing the Shaithalyatha in these Dhatus leading to the manifestation of Kushta Roga.^[4] Further in Chikitsa sthana, he has been explained that the Vatadi Doshas get Prakopa and does Dushana of Twak, Rakta, Mamsa and Ambu leading to seven and eleven types of Maha and Kshudra kushta respectively.^[5]

Treatment of Kushta

All three types of treatment viz. Daivavyapashraya, Yuktivyapashraya and Satvavajaya chikitsa are to be followed while treating Kushta. All varieties of kushta are caused by the simultaneous vitiation of all the three dosas. However, some dosas are predominant and other are not. Keeping this in view, and after ascertaining this from manifested signs and symptoms, the physician should decide the line of Treatment with their Yukti.^[6]

In this study we are dealing with Rasaushadhis in Kushta Chikitsa

Acharya Charaka has mentioned the administration of Lelitaka (Gandhaka) with the juice of Jati (Amalaki) and honey for the treatment of seventeen types of Kushta(Except Kakanaka). He has also prescribed the use of Makshika Dhatu together with cow's urine.^[7] Furthermore, Charaka has described the therapeutic application of Rasa(mercury) processed by adding Gandhaka or svarnamaksika Bhasma in the management of Kushta and another preparation Rasa(mercury) processed with Vajra (Diamond) and Shilajatu or Yogaraja cures all ailments.^[8]

Acharya Sushruta has mentioned Ayaskriti (Lauha Rasayana) in treatment of Kushta. He also mentioned Svarna makshika, Loha churna, Tuttha and Hartala for external application in Shwitra.^[9]

Rasaushadhis mentioned in different classics for Kushta

Rasendra Sara Sangraha ^[10]	Rasendra Chintamani ^[11]	Rasa Ratna Samucchy ^[12]	Rasa Tarangini ^[13]	Rasayoga Sagar ^[14]
1.Mahatalakeswara Rasa 2.Rajarajeswara Rasa 3.Paribhadra Rasa 4.Kushtari Rasa 5.Lankeswara Rasa 6.Kushthanasana churna 7.Kushthakuthara Rasa 8.Arkeswara Rasa 9.Kushtakalanala Rasa 10.Brahma Rasa 11.Galatkushtari Rasa 12.Chandranana	1.Swetari Rasa 2.Udayabhaskara Rasa 3.Rasamanikya 4.Manikya Rasa 5.Vajra vati	1.Arogyavardhini Vati 2.Gandhaka Druti	1.Gandhaka Rasayana 2.Gandhaka Taila 3.Rasa karpura 4.Rasa pushpa	1.Kushta kulantaka Rasa 2.Kusthagaja kesari 3.Kusthaghna Rasa 4.Kusthadalno rasa 5.Kushta nikruntano Rasa 6.Kushta Rudreshwaro Rasa 7.Kushta ankusho Rasa 8.Kusthantako Rasa 9.Gandhaka kalpa (shodash) 10.Talakeshwar Rasa 11.Tala Sindur 12.Rasa-Abhra guggulu

Rasa 13.Harिताleswara Rasa				13.Shitapittabhanjana Rasa 14.Shwitrari Rasa 15.ShwetKusthari Rasa
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Some important Rasa Dravyas which are commonly used in Rasayogas

GANDHAKA

Gandhaka is one of the most popular and commonly used drug in the treatment of skin diseases. It is known by synonyms such as Pamari and Kushthari. Gandhaka is a key ingredient in many formulations used for both internal and external applications in dermatological conditions.

Pharmacologically, Gandhaka possesses Madhura Rasa, Ushna Virya, and Katu Vipaka. It acts as a Yogavahi, Rasayana, and Deepana. Its therapeutic actions include Kandughna, Kusthaghna, Visarpahara, and Krimihara properties. It is especially effective in conditions such as Pama (scabies), Kandu, Dadru (tinea), and Vicharchika (eczema).^[15]

GANDHAKA RASAYANA is the most important formulation of Gandhaka, widely employed in skin diseases. It primarily acts on Rakta Dhatu and Twak. When Raktadushti occurs due to Hetu sevana, it leads to Malinata in the Rasadi Sapta Dhatu, thereby hampering the absorption of essential nutrients. In such conditions, Gandhaka Rasayana purifies the blood (Rakta shuddhi) and re-establishes the proper functioning of the Sapta Dhatu.

It is particularly indicated when the main symptom is Daha (burning sensation) caused by the Tikshnata of Pitta. Gandhaka Rasayana is considered the drug of choice in Pitta-pradhana Maha Kustha and Kshudra Kustha such as Pama.

The recommended dose is ½ to 1 gram, administered along with Daruharidra(Darvi), Haridra, Manjistha, Amalaki, and other suitable Anupana for Kustha. It should be given continuously for one month, followed by a one-month gap, and this cycle can be repeated for up to three years.^[16]

HARTALA

In Charaka Samhita, Haratala is prescribed for external application in various skin disorders. In Chikitasa sthana, Haratala is also indicated for the treatment of skin diseases. In Sushruta Samhita Chikitasa sthana, it is mentioned for Vrana Shodhana, Pandu Karma, various

dermatological conditions, Granthi (nodules), Upadamsa (syphilitic eruptions), Visarpa, and even as a hair remover in different Yogas.

Haratala possesses Katu Rasa, Katu Vipaka, Ushna Virya, and the qualities of Snigdha and Guru Guna. It is Agni-dipaka and Kusthaghna in nature.^[17] Haratala is considered a highly useful medicine in Kustha. In cases of Vata-Kapha predominance, or when these two doshas are primarily vitiated along with Twak, Mamsa, and Lasika as Dushya, Haratala acts like Amruta (Nectar) in the management of Kustha Roga.

Among the seven **Maha Kushtha** (Kapala, Udumbar, Mandala, Sidhma, Kakanaka, Pundarika, and Rushyajivha), Haratala Bhasma can be used in all except Rushyajivha, depending on the involvement of Dosha and Dushya. When the skin becomes blackish or reddish-black, dry, hard, cracked in places, and extremely painful, such Kustha is considered **Vata-Pradhana**, and in these cases Tala Bhasma should be administered. Classical texts also highlight its role in reducing discoloration and improving complexion. However, it should not be given (Contra Indicate) in **Pitta-Pradhana** Kustha.^[18]

RASA MANIKYA is a commonly used formulation of Haratala for skin diseases. It is indicated in conditions such as Galat Kustha, Dushta Vrana, Vicharchika, Pundarika Kustha, Charmadala Kustha, Visphotaka, and Mandala Kustha. It predominantly acts on Vata-Kaphaja Kustha.

Haratala naturally contains both Somala (arsenic) and Gandhaka (sulphur). When Haratala is processed into Bhasma, the entire sulphur content volatilizes and a portion of the arsenic also dissipates. However, when prepared as **Rasa Manikya**, the sulphur undergoes maturation and chemical transformation, while the arsenic content is largely retained; only about 1% of the arsenic is lost through volatilization. Through this specific method of preparation, the arsenic and sulphur within Rasa Manikya form a unique molecular complex that, upon ingestion, rapidly assimilates into the bloodstream and manifests its therapeutic effects immediately.

Rasa Manikya can also be used for external application in Shwitra Kustha (vitiligo), where one part of Rasa Manikya is mixed with two parts of Somaraji(Bakuchi) Churna and Gomutra.

The recommended dose of Rasa Manikya is $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{1}{2}$ Ratti. For Kustha and Rakta vikara, it should be administered with an Anupana of Goghrita and Madhu (honey).^[19]

LOHA BHASMA

Loha Bhasma possesses Madhura, Tikta, and Kashaya Rasa. Its Gunas are Guru and Ruksha, with Sheeta Virya. It exhibits Kapha-Pitta Hara properties and is endowed with Lekhana, Netrya, Balya, Vrishya, Varnya, and Medhya qualities.^[20]

In Pitta-Pradhana Kustha, due to the vitiation of Dosha, Rakta and Twak become Dushta. In such conditions, Loha Bhasma should be administered.

Pitta-Pradhana Kustha presents with symptoms such as burning sensation, redness, thin watery discharge from the skin, blisters or ulcers on the fingers, and wounds that suppurate and rupture easily, even from minor injuries. Occasionally, peeling of the skin on the fingers or breaking of digits may also occur.

In the management of this condition, when skin lesions appear reddish-black and are accompanied by small pustules, itching, and burning sensation, Loha Bhasma combined with Triphala Churna should be administered.^[21]

Important Formulation of Loha Bhasma are Loha parpati, Tapyadi Loha etc. which are commonly used in skin diseases. The recommended dose of Loha Bhasma is 60 mg to 250 mg.

VANGA BHASMA

Vanga Bhasma possesses Tikta and Kashaya Rasa, with Laghu, Ruksha, and Sara Guna, and Sheeta Virya. It is Shleshmaghna and slightly Vata-Prakopaka. Its properties include Medhya, Medohara, Kriminashana, and Rasayana. Vanga Bhasma is considered Param Vranahara and also exhibits Varnya qualities.^[22]

When administered with Anupana of Khadira Twak Kwatha, Vanga Bhasma is useful in skin diseases.^[23] It has beneficial effects in chronic skin disorders. Hartala-marita Vanga Bhasma is particularly effective in Upadamsa-janita Twak Roga.

Among dermatological conditions, it is especially valuable in chronic eczema, characterized by intense itching, darkening and drying of the skin, or the appearance of small pustules and yellowish boils accompanied by thin watery yellow discharge or thick purulent secretion. Internal administration of Vanga Bhasma, alongside topical treatments, provides rapid relief in such conditions. The more chronic the disorder, the more pronounced and evident the

therapeutic action of Vanga Bhasma becomes. It should be administered in extremely minute doses, ideally as small as 1/100th of a Ratti.

In Kitanujanya Karnapaka, where pus discharges from the ear and forms boils where the pus will go, internal administration of Vanga Bhasma along with external application of Dashanga Lepa has proven beneficial.^[24]

Vanga Bhasma can be given in dose of 1 – 2 Ratti.

YASHADA BHASMA

Yashada Bhasma possesses Kashaya and Katu Rasa, with Ruksha Guna and Ushna Virya. Its Doshaghna property is Kapha-Pitta Nashaka. Yashada Bhasma is described as “Shleshmakala Sankochaka” and “Visheshan Vrana Samsrava Rodhanam”.^[25]

In Vicharchika, external application of Yashada Bhasma mixed with Goghrita for seven days provides significant relief.^[27]

Yashada Bhasma is administered in both acute and chronic cases of Urticaria. Regardless of severity-even when the condition penetrates into deeper body tissues-its symptoms are alleviated within a short period through the intake of Yashada Bhasma.^[27] Yashada Bhasma can be given in Dose should be 1-2 Ratti.

Zinc have antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory & Antibacterial properties. It is photoprotecting (against UV-A1 (340–380) and Soothing Agent. Topical zinc oxide for its strong antioxidant and antibacterial action has been also used in treating atopic dermatitis, a chronic inflammatory eczematous dermatosis characterized by the impairment of the skin-barrier function, increased oxidative cellular stress, and bacterial colonization. It can be used in chronic cutaneous ulcer. Zinc also has Anti-pruritic action. It inhibits mast cell degranulation and thereby reduces the secretion of histamine, an important mediator of inflammatory response and an inducer of itch, thereby making it a useful treatment option in pruritic conditions.^[28]

SUVARN MAKSHIKA BHASMA

Suvarna Makshika possesses Madhura and Tikta Rasa, with Laghu Guna and Sheeta Virya. It has Rasayana, Yogavahi and Raktaprasadaka properties, It is Tridoshaghna-especially Kapha-Pittahara and exhibits Kusthaghna qualities.^[29]

Suvarna Makshika is highly effective in disorders characterized by the appearance of fine, minute pimples all over the body accompanied by itching. It is also useful when the skin, nails, and lips become lustreless, particularly following episodes of excessive bleeding or severe diarrhea.

It is beneficial in conditions where the skin becomes dry, rough, and itchy, especially when administered with Anupana of Ananta moola Kwatha.

Rasatantra Sara va Siddhaprayoga Sangraha has also mention its utility in cases of skin darkening accompanied by eruptions of small pimples, swelling and numbness in the fingers and toes, or the appearance of red to black patches on the body. In such conditions, Suvarna Makshika should be administered mixed with Gandhaka Rasayana or with Tulasi Swarasa as Anupana.^[30]

Suvarna Makshika Bhasma can be given in Dose should be 1-3 Ratti.

ABHRAKA BHASMA

Abhraka Bhasma is described as Snigdha, Madhura, and Sheeta in nature. It possesses Keshya and Varnya properties. It is also Yogavahi in nature. In Rasa Tarangini, it is mentioned that Abhraka Bhasma is Medhya and Priti Janayati, and that it reduces the fear associated with Maharogas.^[31]

Abhraka Bhasma can be administered in skin diseases associated with psychological factors. In Rasa Ratna Samuccaya, Abhraka Bhasma is indicated in Kustha Roga with Anupana of Vidanga and Trikatu. In Rasaamrita, Acharya Yadavji Trikamji has mentioned the use of Abhraka Bhasma for Shitapitta.^[32]

Abhraka Bhasma possess Antimicrobial property. It also has Rejuvenating & adaptogenic properties. It balances Doshas & promote tissue rejuvenation, Act as healing agent.^[33]

Abhraka Bhasma can be given in dose of 1-2 Ratti.

VAIKRANTA BHASMA

Vaikranta Bhasma has Tridosahara, Rasayana, Yogavahi properties, and also it is Param Twachya & Kusthahara. Dose should be 1/8 to 1/2 Ratti.^[34]

TAMRA BHASMA

Tamra Bhasma has Kashaya, Madhur, Tikta & Amla Rasa, Katu Vipaka, Shita Virya. Having Saraka, Pittahara, Shleshmanashaka & Lekhana properties. It should be given in 15-60mg of dose.^[35]

Copper is an essential mineral that plays a significant role in various physiological and metabolic processes, including angiogenesis, skin generation and expression and stabilization of extracellular skin proteins; and it also has potent antimicrobial properties. Therefore it can be used in Wound healing for chronic wound.^[36]

Shvitra affects the fourth layer of the skin named as Tamra Twacha as per Ayurveda classics. so Tamra Bhasma can be the target drug for vitiligo. It helps to cure imbalance of Bhrajaka Pitta which govern skin pigmentation and other vitiated Doshas (body humors).^[37]

SWARNA VANGA

Swarna Vanga possesses Sheeta Virya, with Ruksha and Sara Guna, and Tikta, Lavana, and Amla Rasa. Suvarna Vanga is highly effective in treating skin disorders caused by various types of toxins.

It is particularly useful in chronic Pama Roga, recurrent ulcers, weeping eczema, Arunshika, and deeply seated skin diseases.

The recommended dose is 1–2 Ratti.^[38]

TALA SINDUR

In this Rasayana, the main ingredient is Haratala. Haratala possesses Katu Rasa, Katu Vipaka, and is Snigdha in nature. It exhibits Kaphaghna, Kandughna, and Kusthaghna properties. Tala Sindura shares the same qualities as Haratala. This Rasayana is considered less ugra (intense) than Tala Bhasma and Tala Pushpa. In conditions where Tala Bhasma and Tala Pushpa are contraindicated, Tala Sindura can be administered safely. It is particularly useful in Kapha-pradhana or Kapha-Vata-pradhana Kustha Roga.

The recommended dose is 1–2 Ratti, administered with Ardraka Swarasa and either Madhu (honey) or Ghrita (ghee).^[39]

RASA KARPURA

Rasa Karpura is krimi visha nashaka. It alleviates doshas affecting Twak & Rakta. It is also Grahi in nature as it arrests excessive secretions and discharge from vana. Rasa Karpura eradicates Sphota (boils), Chronic pruritus, Mandala Kustha etc.

The study of Rasakarpura on vicharchika (eczema) as internal used reported significant result without any toxic or adverse effect. Amongst mercurial compounds it quite water soluble so it is absorbed through gut and skin and produced effects. Though it resembles to mercuric chloride (HgCl₂) Rasakarpura is a mixture of Mercuric Chloride and other trace elements so it is found less toxic in therapeutic dose.^[40]

Dose of Rasa karpura is very less i.e. 1/64 to 1/32 Ratti.

AROGYAVARDHINI VATI

Arogyavardhini Vati is a classical herbo-mineral formulation. The term Arogya denotes “good health,” while Vardhini signifies “enhancer,” thus implying a medicine that promotes overall well-being. In Rasa Ratna Samuccaya, its phalashruti is described with the phrases “हन्ति कुष्ठान्यशेषतः” (eradicates all types of Kustha) and “सर्वरोगप्रशमनी” (pacifies all diseases).^[41]

This formulation is particularly indicated in the Prathamavastha of Kustha and remains effective up to the stage of Mamsashrita dosha. Though useful in all varieties of Kustha, it shows greater efficacy in Vata-pradhana and Vata-Kapha pradhana types such as Kapala, Mandala, Ek-Kustha, Kitibha, Vipadika, Charmadala, and Alasaka.

In conditions marked by intense itching, eruptions that exude pus, or spots appearing after scratching, Arogyavardhini combined with Manjishthadi Kwatha yields notable results.

When lesions present as hardened patches, thickened skin, dryness of mouth, pustules, and pain of pricking or bursting nature, it is best administered with Haridra decoction or milk.

The recommended dose is Rajakolphalopama (approximately 365 mg to 1 g). However, it is contraindicated in Garbhini (pregnancy), and in states of Daha (burning sensation), Moha (delusion), Trishna (excessive thirst), Bhrama (giddiness), and Pittaja Vyadhi Avastha (conditions dominated by Pitta).^[42]

DISCUSSION

Rasaushadhis hold unique place in the management of skin diseases. Each Rasadravya has specific role in specific condition of disease. Rasaushadhis act swiftly on their targeted site because of their Ashugamitva guna, absorption start right in the oral mucosa. They enhance bioavailability of medication through their Yogavahi guna. Most of the Rasadravyas shows Rasayana property such as Gandhaka, Abhraka, Suvarna makshika, Loha etc. as it is essential in Skin disease Treatment due to their Recurrence habit. Rasaushadhi such as Gandhaka Rasayana shows Antibacterial & Antifungal action (on candida albicans),^[43] Gandhaka Rasayana seems to be an effective treatment of shushka vicharchika. Haratala is the one of the Rasa dravya which is used externally as lepa & internally for most of formulations. Hartala has Deepana, Kusthaghna, Kandughna, Jantughna, Shothahara, Raktashodhaka, Twachya & Balya Properties. It commonly used in Vata – Kapha pradhana Kustha. Rasamanikya one of the important formulations of Hartala used in skin disease have Antimicrobial activity against different pathogenic microbes such as Staph aureus, Staph epidermis, C. albicans, A. niger.^[44]

Vanga Bhasma is useful in chronic eczema. Yashada Bhasma & Suvarna makshika are useful in Kapha – Pitta pradhana Kustha. As Abhraka Bhasma act on Mana, it is useful in psychosomatic disorders, as stress, anxiety, depression worsen the skin condition in that cases Abhraka Bhasma can be used. Abhraka Bhasma has Antimicrobial, Rejuvenating and Adaptogenic properties. Tamra act as an antioxidant and is supreme in enhancing blood circulation. Tamra removes dushita pitta and kapha by its urdhwa-adhoshodhan activity which are the major reasons for skin diseases. It act as Agnivardhana, Lekhana and Kusthaghna.

Talasin dhura shows antimicrobial activity, it is effective against E-coli, Staph aureus, Candida albicans & Staph mutans.^[45] Rasa karpura shows total inhibition to Streptococcus pyrogens, moderate inhibition to Streptococcus aureus.^[46]

Arogyavardhini vati is Pachaka, Deepana, Baddha kosta and Koshtagata vata nashaka, Samyaka pittasravaka and Srotoshodhaka in nature. It is useful in all type of kustha but mainly in vata pradhana and vata-Kapha Pradhan Kustha.

Varnya dravyas hold significant importance in dermatological conditions, Rasa dravyas having varnya properties are Loha, Vanga, Abhraka etc. All the minerals used in formulations for skin disease are not directly act on skin disease but has supporting role to treat skin disease due to their rasayana property, capacity of improving dhatu pariposhan krama, Srotoshodhana, raktaprasadan and raktavrudhikar property.

CONCLUSION

Nearly 98 Rasakalpas are described in classical texts such as Rasachintamani, Rasendra Sara Sangraha, and Rasaratna Samuchchaya for the management of skin diseases. Among these, Gandhaka is most prominently employed, with Hartala also being a commonly used Rasadravya. In addition, various Bhasmas—including Loha, Tamra, Vanga, Yashada, and Abhraka—are incorporated in different formulations, each selected according to the predominance of Doshas and the specific condition of the skin disorder.

Every Bhasma contributes a distinct therapeutic role, and their judicious combination in Rasaushadhis enhances efficacy. Modern pharmacological studies further substantiate their traditional use, highlighting antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory properties. With their high potency, low dosage requirement, and rapid action, Rasaushadhis stand out as powerful agents Skin disease management.

Thus, Rasaushadhis represent a vital contribution of Ayurveda to skin disease management, and their continued exploration and validation may prove to be a boon for integrative healthcare.

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